

BABUR'S PERSONALITY IN "BABURNAME"

Khamdamov Bekhzod Khabibovich

Assistant Department "Social Sciences"

Bukhara State Medical Institute.

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Abstract. *In this article, the author analyzed and described the sociocultural and scientific environment of Transoxiana and India in the 16th-17th centuries. The reasons for the stability and prosperity of the Mughal state, and the collapse of the empire. The author identifies the factors for the remarkable growth of the culture of the Mughal Empire.*

Key words: *Great Mughals, heyday, fragmentation, centralization, empire, culture.*

ЛИЧНОСТЬ БАБУРА В «БАБУРНАМЕ»

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор проанализировал и описал социокультурную и научную среду Трансоксианы и Индии в XVI-XVII веках. Причины стабильности и процветания государства Великих Моголов и распада империи. Автор выделяет факторы замечательного роста культуры Империи Великих Моголов.*

Ключевые слова: *Великие Моголы, период расцвета, раздробленность, централизация, империя, культура.*

"Boburnoma" is one of the historical and literary monuments. This is Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483 - 1530), who managed to collect and skillfully present valuable materials for historians, ethnographers, geographers, linguists, and anyone studying the social structure and political life of the peoples of Central Asia.) is an autobiography. Iran, Afghanistan and North India at the end of XV-XVI centuries. "Babur-nama" is also of great importance for the history of the culture of the peoples of the East, because compared to many other historical sources of its time, this work has undeniable advantages both in terms of content and the style of description. presentation.

In all times, when talking about the phenomenon of Babur, his role as a ruler and a poet is meant. The former cannot exceed the latter. And the goal of his destiny: rule and poetry. The fate associated with two incompatible types of activity can lead to something insurmountable: government policy, the sad suffering of creativity ...

Babur's works - "Babur-nama" and sad Rubaiyats show both the ruler Babur, who experienced great suffering, and the poet Babur, who experienced them in his heart, and do not give the opportunity to think otherwise. These ideas about Babur are loved by world readers in such works as "Babur the Tiger", "Prince of Ferghana", "Dervish in the Crown", "Babur", "Babur", "Babur", "Babur", "Babur" It is also evident in the novel. It is common among Uzbek book lovers.

All these works were written on the basis of "Boburnoma". "Boburnoma" is a huge and unique treasure. All information - information, descriptions, interpretations and interpretations in them - always has its own valuable value.

To read "Babur-nama" is to know Babur. The desire to get to know Babur more closely, to experience his spiritual joys and sufferings with him invites us to read his poems. We read poetry.

And our heart is as wide as the sky, it seems as if something is tormenting our soul, feeling the blood flowing in our veins, and beginning to recognize Babur, who is searching for himself and his destiny.

Yes, no matter how much the poet searched the pages of life and looked for the star of happiness in heaven, he could not find it. If it is not possible to find what you want in the destiny, isn't a person who sees good and bad indifferent to the opinions and accusations of others? Having experienced so much suffering, the poet realized the "value" of other people's words very early.

"Baburnoma" should be read in order to get to know Babur's personality closely and to understand him. And we participate together with Babur in his battles, struggles for survival, and his great works to build a great state. Lands, countries conquered sometimes in battles, sometimes peacefully, discoveries after losses.

This work, which the author himself called "Vakoye" - "History of Events", is an expression of Babur's heart. All the talent of Babur the ruler and Babur the poet is shown in it. In a certain part of the work, Babur, who strives to realize his big dream through battles in difficult trials and wanderings, appears in the image of a demanding and skillful general. With his small army, he managed to destroy the large army of Sultan Ibrahim in half a day, and the author of "Babur-nama" writes: "... To the troops assigned to go around the mirzas were ordered to go. the rear, right and left side of the enemy, shooting arrows and connecting the battle; both the right and left flanks had to move and engage with the enemy.

Heavy detachments went behind enemy lines and began firing. Mahdikhoja on the left side started to fight before everyone else. A detachment [led by] an elephant moved against Mahdi Khwaja.

Mahdikhoja's men fired a lot of shots and forced this detachment to retreat. Ahmadi the propeller, Tardi Beg, Kuch Beg [son] and Muhibb Ali, [son] Khalifa were sent from the center to help the left wing.

A battle also broke out on the right bank; Mohammadi Kokeltash, Shah Mansur Barlos, Yunus Ali and Abdullah were ordered to form in front of the center and start the battle. Ustoz Ali Quli shot several times from the ball standing in front of the center. Mustafa Topchi also shot twice from a gun mounted on a cart on the left side of the center. The right division, the left division, the central detachment and the fighters who passed behind the enemy surrounded the enemy from all sides, bombarded them with hail and began a serious fight.

There are many such details about the wars that took place in the pages of "Boburnoma".

But such a description of events does not allow us to evaluate "Boburnoma" as a work only about battles. That's why great scientists and politicians who compared Babur with Julius Caesar emphasize that he is a charming person and the owner of a kind heart, and consider "Baburnoma" to be higher than "Tafsir" of Caesar, because Babur's work is a great person with a huge heart.

Babur, whose life was spent mainly in trials and wanderings, always learned to restrain himself.

He held himself accountable for every act, and when he did something unworthy, he looked for the reason for it, and in most cases, he found the reason in himself and tried to correct his mistake. Of course, the joy of youth, the spirit of freedom, the burning desires of the heart often attracted him.

There are many such interpretations and superstitions in "Boburnoma". In particular, the author's description of events.

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